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A DOUBLE PERIODIC SYSTEM OF RECTILINEAR CRACKS WITH CONNECTIONS BETWEEN THE EDGES

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Annotation: The problem of tension and shear of a thin isotropic plate weakened by a doubly periodic system of rectilinear cracks with end zones is considered. General representations of solutions are constructed that describes a class of problems with a doubly periodic stress distribution outside cracks. The main singular integral equation of the problem is reduced to an infinite system of algebraic equations. Due to the unknown size of the end zone, the system of equations turned out to be non-linear even with a linear bond deformation law.

Keywords: tension, rectilinear cracks, singular integral equation, non-linear equations, deformation

ДВУХПЕРИОДИЧЕСКАЯ СИСТЕМА ПРЯМОЛИНЕЙНЫХ ТРЕЩИН С СОЕДИНЕНИЯМИ МЕЖДУ КРАЯМИ

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Аннотация: Рассмотрена задача о растяжении и сдвиге тонкой изотропной пластины, ослабленной двоякопериодической системой прямолинейных трещин с концевыми зонами. Построены общие представления решений, описывающие класс задач с

двокопериодическим распределением напряжений вне трещин. Основное сингулярное интегральное уравнение задачи сводится к бесконечной системе алгебраических уравнений. Из-за неизвестного размера концевой зоны система уравнений оказалась нелинейной даже при линейном законе деформации связи.

Ключевые слова: растяжение, прямолинейные трещины, сингулярное интегральное уравнение, нелинейные уравнения, деформации

Let mean stresses N_1, N_2 and N_{12} act in an unbounded isotropic plate weakened by a doubly periodic system of rectilinear cracks. We assume that on the crack faces outside the end zones, the same at congruent points, self-balanced loads $F^\pm(x)$ are given.

Let us single out parts of the crack with lengths d_1 and d_2 (end regions) adjacent to its vertices ($-\ell \leq x \leq -\ell + d_1$ and $\ell - d_2 \leq x \leq \ell, y = 0$). We believe that their dimensions, which are not known in advance, can be comparable with the crack size. The interaction of the crack faces in the end region is modeled by introducing bonds between the crack faces having a given deformation diagram. Under the action of external loads, normal $q_y(x)$ and tangential forces $q_{xy}(x)$ will appear in the bonds between the crack faces. The values of these stresses are not known in advance and must be determined in the process of solving the problem of fracture mechanics.

Let us denote the main periods ω_1 and ω_2 ($\text{Im}\omega_1 = 0, \text{Im}(\frac{\omega_2}{\omega_1}) > 0$), the area occupied by the plate material, through D ; the beginnings and ends of the cracks will be placed, respectively, at the points

$$-\ell + m\omega_1 + n\omega_2, \ell + m\omega_1 + n\omega_2, (m, n = 0, \pm 1, \pm \dots; 0 \leq \ell < \omega_1/2).$$

Due to the symmetry of the boundary conditions and the geometry of the domain D , the stresses in D are doubly periodic functions with basic periods ω_1 and ω_2 .

We seek the solution to the problem in the form [4, 7].

$$\begin{aligned}\Phi(z) &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\ell}^{\ell} p(x) \zeta(x-z) dx + A, \\ \bar{\Omega}(z) &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\ell}^{\ell} \{F(x) - \overline{p(x)}\} \zeta(x-z) dx + \\ &+ \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\ell}^{\ell} p(x) \{\rho_1(x-z) - (x-z)\rho(x-z) + \zeta(x-z)\} dx + B.\end{aligned}\quad (1)$$

Here $F(x) = F^+(x) - F^-(x)$; $\rho(z)$ and $\zeta(z)$ are Weierstrass functions, $\rho_1(z)$ is a special meromorphic function; $F(x)$ – jump of the expression $\sigma_y(x) + i\tau_{xy}(x)$ on the cracked edges $[-\ell + d_1, \ell - d_2]$; A and B are constants determined by static conditions, $p(x)$ is the desired function on $(-\ell, \ell)$.

To the basic representations (1), it is necessary to add equality expressing the condition for the uniqueness of displacements in D :

$$\int_{-\ell}^{\ell} p(x) dx = 0. \quad (2)$$

From the conditions of double periodicity and the existence of given average stresses N_1, N_2 and N_{12} in D , we find the constants A and B in the following form

$$\begin{aligned}\operatorname{Re} A &= \frac{1}{4}(\sigma_1 + \sigma_2) - \frac{\pi}{2S} f - \frac{1}{\omega_1} R(a\delta_1), \quad S = \omega_1 \cdot \operatorname{Im} \omega_2, \\ B - A &= \frac{1}{2}(\sigma_2 - \sigma_1) + i\tau - \frac{\pi - \delta_1 \cdot \operatorname{Im} \omega_2}{S} f - \frac{a\gamma_1}{\omega_1} - \frac{\pi\delta_1}{\omega_1}.\end{aligned}\quad (3)$$

Here $\sigma_2 = N_2 \sin \alpha$, $\tau = N_{12} + N_2 \cos \alpha$, $\sigma_1 \sin \alpha = N_1 + 2N_{12} \cos \alpha + N_2 \cos^2 \alpha$, σ_1, σ_2, τ – the average stresses on the areas perpendicular to the coordinate axes Ox and Oy .

$$a = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{-\ell}^{\ell} xp(x) dx; \quad f = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{-\ell}^{\ell} xF(x) dx. \quad (4)$$

The conditions of double periodicity of stresses will be satisfied by choosing the desired functions (1), so it is sufficient to satisfy the boundary conditions only on the banks of the main crack.

These boundary conditions have the form [6]:

$$\bar{\Omega}(x) + \overline{\Phi(x)} = \begin{cases} F^+(x_0) & x = x_0 + 0i \\ F^-(x_0) & x = x_0 - 0i \end{cases}, \quad x_0 \in [-\ell + d_1, \ell - d_2], \quad (5)$$

$$\bar{\Omega}(x) + \overline{\Phi(x)} = q_y + iq_{xy} \text{ at end zones } (-\ell, -\ell + d_1) \text{ и } (\ell - d_2, \ell).$$

The main ratios of the problem posed should be supplemented by an equation that relates the opening of the crack edges and the forces in the bonds.

This equation in the problem under consideration can be represented, according to [1, 2], in the form

$$(v^+ - v^-) - i(u^+ - u^-) = C(x, \sigma)[q_y(x) - iq_{xy}(x)],$$

$$\sigma = \sqrt{q_y^2 + q_{xy}^2} \tag{6}$$

The function $C(x, \sigma)$ can be considered as the effective compliance of bonds, depending on their tension; σ is the module of the force vector in the bonds; $(v^+ - v^-)$ – normal, $(u^+ - u^-)$ – tangential component of the opening of crack edges in the end zone.

Substituting the limiting values of the functions $\overline{\Phi(x)}$ and $\overline{\Omega}(z)$ into the boundary condition (5), we obtain a singular integral equation for $p(x)$

$$\frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{-\ell}^{\ell} \overline{p(x)} \{ \zeta(x - x_0) + \overline{\zeta(x - x_0)} \} dx - \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\ell}^{\ell} p(x) \{ \rho_1(x - x_0) - (x - x_0)\rho(x - x_0) + \zeta(x - x_0) \} dx - B - \bar{A} = G(x_0), \tag{7}$$

where at $x_0 \in [-\ell + d_1, \ell - d_2]$: $G(x_0) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{-\ell}^{\ell} F(x) \zeta(x - x_0) dx - \frac{F^+(x) + F^-(x)}{2}$

at $-\ell \leq x_0 \leq \ell + d_1$ and $\ell - d_2 \leq x_0 \leq \ell$: $G(x_0) = q_y + iq_{xy}$.

Using the expansions $\zeta(z), \rho(z)$ and $\rho_1(z)$ in the main period parallelogram [5].

$$\zeta(z) = \frac{1}{z} - \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{g_{j+1} z^{2j+1}}{\omega_1^{2j+2}}, \quad g_k = \sum_{m,n} \cdot \frac{1}{T^{2k}},$$

$$\rho(z) = \frac{1}{z^2} + \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2j+1)g_{j+1}}{\omega_1^{2j+2}} z^{2j}, \quad \rho_k^* = \sum_{m,n} \cdot \frac{\bar{T}}{T^{2k+1}},$$

$$\rho_1(z) = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2j+2)\rho_{2j+1}^*}{\omega_1^{2j+2}} z^{2j+1},$$

$$T = m + n \frac{\omega_2}{\omega_1}, \quad m, n = 0, \pm 1, \pm \dots, \quad k = 2, 3, \dots$$

Equation (7) after some simple transformations will be reduced to the form

$$\frac{1}{\pi i} \int_{-1}^1 \frac{g(\xi)}{\xi - \xi_0} d\xi - \frac{1}{\pi i} \int_{-1}^1 g(\xi) K(\xi - \xi_0) d\xi - \frac{1}{\pi i} \int_{-1}^1 \overline{g(\xi)} K_*(\xi - \xi_0) d\xi = G_1(\xi_0), \tag{8}$$

Where

$$g(\xi) = p(x), \quad \xi = \frac{x}{\ell}, \quad \xi_0 = \frac{x_0}{\ell}, \quad \lambda = \frac{2\ell}{\omega_1}, \quad -1 < \xi_0 < 1,$$

$$K(\xi) = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} K_j \left(\frac{\lambda}{2}\right)^{2j+2} \xi^{2j+1}, K_0 = \omega_1 \operatorname{Re} \delta_1,$$

$$K_*(\xi) = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} K_j^* \left(\frac{\lambda}{2}\right)^{2j+2} \xi^{2j+1}, 0 \leq \lambda < 1,$$

$$K_j = \operatorname{Re} g_{j+1}, K_0^* = -\frac{\omega_1}{2} (\gamma_1 + \delta_1),$$

$$K_j^* = (j+1)(\bar{\rho}_{j+1}^* - \bar{g}_{j+1}), j = 1, 2, \dots,$$

$$G_1(\xi_0) = i\tau - \sigma_2 + iq_{xy} - q_y \text{ при } -1 \leq \xi_0 \leq -1 + \frac{d_1}{\ell} \text{ и } 1 - \frac{d_2}{\ell} \leq \xi_0 \leq 1,$$

$$G_1(\xi_0) = i\tau - \sigma_2 + \frac{1}{2}\{F^+(x_0) + F^-(x_0)\} + \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{-\ell}^{\ell} \overline{F(x)} \left\{ \overline{\zeta(x-x_0)} - \frac{x\delta_1}{\omega_1} \right\} dx,$$

$$F(x) = F^+(x) - F^-(x).$$

To the singular equation (8) it is necessary to add equality (2) in the following form

$$\int_{-1}^1 g(\xi) d\xi = 0. \quad (9)$$

If the plate and the external load are symmetrical concerning the coordinate axes, then equation (8) degenerates into one singular integral equation concerning the function $g(\xi)$, which takes purely imaginary values. In the general case, equation (8) is a system of two singular integral equations concerning the complex function $g(\xi)$.

A singular integral equation can be reduced to an infinite system of algebraic equations. We accept that according to [5, 8]:

$$g(\xi) = \frac{g_0(\xi)}{\sqrt{1-\xi^2}}, \quad (10)$$

where $g_0(\xi)$ is Gelder continuous on $[-1,1]$ function.

We will search for $g_0(\xi)$ g_0 as a series in Chebyshev polynomials of the first kind. We have

$$g_0(\xi) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} A_k T_k(\xi), T_k(\xi) = \cos(k \arccos \xi) \quad (11)$$

Substituting (10), (11) into the singular integral equation (8), as well as using the relations for the Chebyshev polynomials of the first and second series $T_k(\xi)$ and $U_k(\xi)$ and the orthogonality of the functions $U_k(\xi)$ on $[-1,1]$, we obtain an infinite system of algebraic equations concerning the coefficients A_k :

$$A_{k+1} - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} C_{nk} A_n - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} C_{nk}^* \bar{A}_n = iD_k, k = 0, 1, \quad (12)$$

where

$$C_{nk} = \frac{2}{\pi^2} \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 \frac{T_n(\xi)U_k(\xi_0)\sqrt{1-\xi_0^2}}{\sqrt{1-\xi^2}} K(\xi - \xi_0)d\xi d\xi_0,$$

$$C_{nk}^* = \frac{2}{\pi^2} \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 \frac{T_n(\xi)U_k(\xi_0)\sqrt{1-\xi_0^2}}{\sqrt{1-\xi^2}} K_*(\xi - \xi_0)d\xi d\xi_0,$$

$$D_k = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_{-1}^1 G_1(\xi_0)U_k(\xi_0)\sqrt{1-\xi_0^2}d\xi_0.$$

The coefficients C_{nk}, C_{nk}^* can be represented explicitly.

Using (7) and relations for the Chebyshev polynomials of the first and second series $T_k(\xi)$ and $U_k(\xi)$, we find

$$C_{nk} = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\lambda}{2}\right)^{2j+2} \cdot K_j \alpha_{jnk}, \quad C_{nk}^* = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\lambda}{2}\right)^{2j+2} \cdot K_j^* \alpha_{jnk}, \quad (13)$$

$$\alpha_{jnk} = 2 \sum_{s=0}^{2j+1} (-1)^s \frac{(2j+1)!}{s!(2j+1-s)!} a_{k,s} b_{n,2j-s+1}.$$

The value d characterizing the length of the end zones enter the solution of system (12) as an unknown parameter to be determined. Since the stresses in the plate material are limited, the solution of the singular integral equation (8) should be sought in the class of everywhere limited functions (stresses). The condition of limited stresses at the ends $x = \pm\ell$ serves to determine the parameters d_1 and d_2 , knowing which one can find the lengths of the end zones. In general, the size of the end zones at the left and right ends of the crack will be different.

To ensure the finiteness of stresses at the left and right ends of cracks, it is necessary to add the following conditions to the system (12):

$$\sqrt{\pi\ell g_0(1)} = \sqrt{\pi\ell} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \bar{A}_k = 0,$$

$$\sqrt{\pi\ell g_0(-1)} = \sqrt{\pi\ell} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^k \bar{A}_k = 0. \quad (14)$$

System (12) includes unknown values of forces q_y and q_{xy} at nodal points belonging to the end zones of cracks.

Based on the ratio: $\Phi^+(x) - \Phi^-(x) = \frac{2\mu}{1+\kappa_0} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} (u^+ - u^-) + i \frac{\partial}{\partial x} (v^+ - v^-) \right]$

and formula (1), we obtain an equation for the unknown function $q_y + iq_{xy}$:

$$p(x) = \frac{2\mu}{1+\kappa_0} \frac{d}{dx} [C(x, \sigma)(q_y + iq_{xy})]. \quad (15)$$

To construct the missing equations, we require the fulfillment of conditions (15) at the nodal points contained in the end zones of the crack. As a result, we obtain an algebraic system of M_1 equations for determining approximate values $q_y(t_m) + iq_{xy}(t_m)$ ($m = 1, 2, \dots, M_1$).

The resulting algebraic systems (12), (14), and (15) turned out to be related and are solved jointly. Due to the unknown sizes of the end zones, the system of equations (12), (14), and (15) is non-linear even with linear constraints.

To solve it, we used the method of successive approximations [5], the essence of which is as follows.

We solve the algebraic system (12), (15) for some specific values of d_{1*} and d_{2*} concerning the unknowns A_k ($k = 1, 2, \dots, M$) and $q_y + iq_{xy}$. The unknowns $A_k, q_y + iq_{xy}$ enter the system linearly. This circumstance justifies the use of the proposed method. The values of d_{1*} and d_{2*} and the found values of the coefficients A_k are substituted into the unused equations (14). The taken values of the parameters d_{1*} and d_{2*} and the corresponding values of the coefficients A_k will not, generally speaking, satisfy equations (14). Therefore, choosing the values of the parameters d_1 and d_2 , we will repeatedly repeat the calculations until the last equations of system (14) are satisfied with a given accuracy.

Calculations were obtained depending on the size of the end zones depending on the relative size of the region $\lambda = 2\ell/\omega_1$ ($\omega_2 = \omega_1 e^{i\pi/3}$ and $\omega_2 = \omega_1 e^{i\pi/2}$) and tensile stresses. The crack faces were considered to be free from loads. In the case of a nonlinear law of deformation of bonds, an algorithm similar to the method of elastic solutions [3] was also used to determine the forces in the end zones. To determine the limit-equilibrium state, we use the condition of critical crack opening.

Для определения предельно-равновесного состояния используем условие критического раскрытия трещины.

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